

Design a new functional food using inulin as a substitute for fats and sugars in cookie formulations.

Jorge L. Vergel-Berrio¹; Olga T. Jaimes P.;² María Hernández-Carrión³
Universidad de los Andes, Colombia

Inulin, recognized for its properties as a functional food ingredient, emerges as a promising element to enrich the nutritional value of foods. This study focused on including prebiotic function in cookies, a widely consumed food, by incorporating inulin. Three formulations were designed that partially substituted sugar or fat content compared to a control sample. The evaluation covered the resulting cookies' physical, textural, and sensory properties. It was highlighted that the replacement of inulin by fat negatively affected quality, manifesting in a significant increase in hardness and color changes, corroborated by sensory panel perceptions. In contrast, the exclusive substitution of sugar content preserved the properties of the control cookie, with minimal variations in moisture and water activity. However, both the control cookie and the variant with sugar replacement obtained the best results in the sensory analyses and showed higher purchase intention. Consequently, the formulation with sugar replacement was identified as the most successful, showing significant potential for its introduction in the national market.

Keywords: Functional food, Inulin, Fats, Sugars.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15880863

¹ Chemical Engineer and Master in Process and Product Design. Contact: jl.vergel@uniandes.edu.co

² Nutritionist Dietitian and Master in Food Science and Technology. Contact: ojaimes@unisinucartagena.edu.co

³ Chemical Engineer, Master in Food Science and Engineering and PhD in Science, Technology and Food Management. Contact: m.hernandez1@uniandes.edu.co

1. INTRODUCTION

Functional foods are defined as those foods or ingredients that provide additional health benefits beyond the normal or basic nutritional properties of the product [1, 2]. The term was first used more than 50 years ago, and currently, the industry continues to innovate in the field, making it increasingly common to find these products on our table. These foods possess elements with biological activity that improve the physical condition of the individual, helping in the prevention of diseases and improving the quality of life [2]. Some of the functions they perform include: acting as hormone regulators, promoting biotic growth, and improving the digestion of nutrients, among others, and nowadays they can be found in almost any type of product, such as dairy products, meat products, integrated cereals and beverages [3].

Inulin has been identified as a functional food ingredient that can improve the nutritional value of foods. It is a non-digestible carbohydrate extracted from the roots of some vegetables such as chicory, garlic, and onion [4]. This product offers great functional benefits, which make it ideal to be incorporated into food products to improve their nutritional properties and organoleptic characteristics. Inulin acts as a prebiotic and induces changes in the epithelium and functions of the colon [5]. They selectively ferment in the colon and cause changes in the intestinal microflora, serving as a selective *fertilizer* for the colonic microflora that ferments it [5, 6].

In addition, inulin improves bowel habits in terms of stool frequency and weight by functioning as a dietary fiber and improving fecal bulk [5-7]. It is classified as a dietary fiber based on its resistance to digestion and provides strong evidence of a prebiotic effect by selectively stimulating the growth of bifidobacterial in the colonic microbiota [5, 6]. This set of functions means that people who consume inulin in sufficient amounts have benefits related to reducing the risk of intestinal diseases and cardiovascular diseases. Finally, inulin has a low caloric content compared to other carbohydrates, which makes it a good alternative to be used as a substitute.

The incorporation of inulin in functional foods presents several challenges, as it can alter the sensory properties of the product. One possible challenge is that it can affect the flavor and produce a different texture, which may be unattractive to some consumers. Another point to consider is that the addition of inulin can affect the physical properties of certain foods. For example, the incorporation of inulin in cakes may cause changes in the browning of the crust, yellowing of the dough, hardness, and stickiness, which may affect the overall acceptability of the product [8].

In addition, the functionality of inulin will depend on the food matrix to which it is added. In some cases, inulin can benefit the growth of good bacteria, as seen in the case of probiotic yogurt, while in other cases it can act as a texture improver, for example in cereals and baked goods [4]. Therefore, it is important to consider the specific properties of each food product when including inulin as an ingredient. This is to ensure that the desired functional benefits are achieved, without sacrificing consumer acceptability or product quality.

Inulin is currently widely used in the food sector, especially in meat products (such as sausages and hamburgers), dairy products (such as yogurts), and baked products (such as cakes and cookies). Some of the technological functions they perform in products are fat replacement, providing stability and texture; emulsion stabilizer, improving sensory attributes; sugar replacement, presenting synergy with sweeteners; prebiotic function, providing fiber and increasing water retention capacity [4].

In this context, it was decided to develop a study to find the impact that the incorporation of inulin has on the properties of a baked product, in this case, cookies. Cookies present numerous advantages as a food matrix for this study, such as a relatively simple manufacturing process and the absence of complex storage conditions for its ingredients. They are a common consumer product around the world and are characterized by their diversity in formulations, shapes, and ingredients. As a popular snack, they offer the opportunity to adjust both their composition and manufacturing process to achieve specific properties in the final product, such as texture, flavor, and color, among other aspects. In addition, their versatile matrix facilitates the incorporation of new ingredients in their formulation [9].

In this study, the effect of the incorporation of inulin in a baked product of the butter cookie type was evaluated and its characterization was carried out. For this purpose, three new formulations were made in which the percentage of fat and sugar replaced by inulin powder was varied concerning a control formulation, to define the best of the new formulations. This was done using organoleptic, physical, and nutritional tests, which were compared using an analysis of variance to evaluate the effect of variations in the percentages of fat and sugar on the physicochemical properties and acceptance of the product.

2. METHOD

It was decided to make a control formulation and three formulations with different proportions of inulin. Inulin acts as a sugar or fat replacement in the formulations concerning the control formulation. The reason for this is also to determine whether inulin has a better effect when replacing fat or sugar, in terms of physical and organoleptic properties. For all trials, at least triplicate tests are performed for each sample group, under recommended storage conditions (hermetically sealed at low humidity and room temperature).

2.1 Cookie formulation and preparation

The ingredients used to prepare the doughs were wheat flour (Haz de oros®), unsalted butter (Alpina®), sugar (Manuelita®), eggs A (Megatiendas), baking powder (Levapan®), salt (Refisal®), powdered milk (Klim®) and inulin (Smart Chemical®).

The dough was prepared using the following process. Initially, the butter and sugar were mixed in a mixer at maximum speed for 14 minutes, which is the time measured until the cream was incorporated and no sugar crystals were perceived in the mixture. The egg was then added to the cream mixture using a hand mixer. As a final step, the dry ingredients (flour, milk powder, salt, baking powder, and inulin), which were previously sieved with a kitchen strainer to facilitate incorporation, were added progressively for 2 minutes at maximum speed.

The mixture was kneaded and rolled out with a rolling pin, and the cookies were cut out with a 5 cm diameter mold, with a dough thickness of approximately 5 mm. The cookies were placed on a greased baking tray and placed in a convection oven (Rational. I combi pro, Germany) preheated to 181°C for 12 minutes.

Following a review of studies where inulin was used in baked product formulations to replace sugars [10, 11] and fat [12, 13], it was decided to carry out an experimental design where the sugar and fat content was varied, taking into account the feasibility observed by the results in the studies cited. Three new formulations were made from modifications to a control formulation: the first had a replacement of 30% by weight of the fat content by RG inulin, the second had a replacement of 30% of the sugar content by RA inulin, and the third RGA had a replacement of 15% of the fat content and 15% of the sugar content by inulin (Table 1).

Table 1. Cookie dough formulations (% w/w).

Ingredient	Control	RG	RA	RGA
Flour	47.5	47.5	47.5	47.5
Butter	23.7	16.6	23.7	20.2
Sugar	19.0	19.0	13.3	16.1
Egg	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
Powdered milk	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
Salt	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Baking powder	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Inulin	0.0	7.1	5.7	6.4

2.2 DSC Analysis

This test was performed to know the changes in the energy of the material due to temperature change. DSC differential scanning calorimetry was performed on the DSC Q2000 equipment for a pure inulin sample, to understand the phenomena given during the baking process.

This was carried out by first heating an inulin sample of approximately 5 mg with a constant heating rate of 10°C/min from room temperature (25°C) to 110°C, followed by cooling to 20°C, then another heating cycle to 110°C, followed by cooling to 20°C and ending with heating to 210°C [14].

2.3 TGA analysis

In this procedure, the changes in the mass of a cookie sample for each formulation (Control, RG, RA, RGA) were recorded when heated from room temperature to 600°C with a ramp of 10°C/min. The objective of the test was to identify the temperatures where there are higher mass losses of the material, corresponding to the degradation of its components [15]. The thermogravimetric analysis was performed on the SDT Q600 equipment.

2.4 Texture measurement

For the characterization of the cookies, a three-point bending test was performed to measure the hardness and tractability of each cookie after baking. In this test, a force was applied from a punch approaching at a constant speed to the sample object. The equipment recorded the force that the geometry opposes during its travel and results in a stress on the cookie called hardness. The test was performed on a texturometer, at a speed of 1 mm/s up to a target distance of 5 mm. The test was performed for five cookies per sample group [16].

2.5 Colorimetric analysis

The surface color of the formulated cookies was evaluated to compare whether there was a color change concerning the Control sample. This test was performed with a solid colorimeter (CR-20 Konica Minolta, Japan) with a standard illuminant D65 and a viewing angle of 8°. The results were expressed in the CIELAB system, using the parameters L*(brightness), a* (green-red coordinates), and b* (yellow-blue coordinates) [17]. Three measurements were performed on the surface of each cookie, and 5 cookies per sample group were evaluated. In addition, the color difference was quantified with equation (1) concerning the control cookie [16].

$$\Delta E = [(L^*)^2 + (a^*)^2 + (b^*)^2]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

This quantification made it possible to determine whether the color differences were perceptible to the human eye. This is as follows: if $\Delta E < 1$ the color differences are not obvious to the human eye, if $1 < \Delta E < 3$ some color differences can be appreciated by the human eye, if $\Delta E > 3$ the color differences are obvious to the human eye [11].

2.6 Moisture content

The moisture content of cookie samples, ranging from 2 g to 5 g, was calculated using a convection oven at 105°C (Mettler UFB-500, Germany) for 2h. 6 samples per group were analyzed [18].

2.7 Water activity A_w

Using a water activity meter, measurements were made on samples of 5 g of cookie. The A_w value has a range between 0 and 1. The higher the value, the more suitable environment for microorganisms to grow is expected and, therefore, it is associated with the shelf life of the food. Thus, low values for this indicator are sought [19].

2.8 Sensory analysis

The organoleptic properties of the four formulations were evaluated by a panel of 50 untrained persons, using a protocol previously endorsed by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Engineering of the

Universidad de los Andes, under project number 542. Each formulation was previously assigned a random three-digit number, to identify them during the procedure. The participants, who were previously informed by written consent about the risks and methodology of the procedure, were given the four cookies with the freedom to choose the order in which they performed the evaluation.

To cleanse the palate, participants were advised to eat soda crackers and take a sip of water between each cracker evaluation. Participants rated overall taste properties, appearance, flavor, taste, texture, and color using a 9-point hedonic scale, where 1 represents *I dislike it very much*; 5 *I neither like nor dislike it*; and 9 *I like it very much*. In addition, sweetness and crunchiness properties were evaluated using a five-point JAR scale (*Just about right*), where: 1 represents *Very little*; 3 *Adequate*; and 5 *Too much* [17].

2.9 Analysis of variance ANOVA

For the statistical comparison of the results, Minitab® 18 software was used. The null hypothesis that the mean of the response groups obtained (for each method: moisture, texture, among others) are statistically equal with 95% confidence when a change of factor (replacement in the formulation) was used was evaluated using a single-factor ANOVA analysis of variance. In addition, Fisher confidence intervals were constructed to compare between sample groups.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DSC Analysis

The results obtained from the differential scanning calorimetry test are presented in detail in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Thermal profile of DSC cycles

An endothermic phase related to the evaporation of the moisture contained in the sample was identified for the first cycle, which is subsequently observed again in the second cycle with much less magnitude. In the third heating, a distinctive step was observed in the curve indicating a glass transition phase, which begins at approximately 108°C T_g, consistent with results for inulin samples with low moisture levels. This transition is characterized by a decrease in the heat capacity of the material, which results in a change in its physical properties, manifesting in a less viscous state. The decrease in viscosity can influence the microscopic structure of the material by providing greater mobility to the molecules, which must be taken into account in terms of its storage.

The observed T_g depends on the sample moisture, crystallinity, and degree of DP polymerization [20]. The degree of polymerization is understood as the size distribution of the polysaccharide chains (in this case fructose) that make up the carbohydrate polymer. According to the results of [21], as the DP increases, the range for T_g decreases, and in turn increases the ability of the material to adsorb moisture due to its increased number of active sites. Water causes the molecules to lose rigidity and compactness, resulting in impairments to the structure and mobility of molecules. These results indicate that the inulin should be stored in conditions of low humidity and temperature close to room temperature to avoid generating changes in the structure of the material, which could affect the properties that are sought to be implemented in the final product.

3.2 TGA analysis

Figure 2a shows the behavior of the thermogravimetric analyses performed under an inert atmosphere with a constant flow of nitrogen.

Figure 2. TGA analysis for pure inulin and samples of the four cookie formulations. (a) Percent mass of sample with increasing temperature from 0°C to 600°C. (b) Derivative of percent mass versus temperature from the same assay.

Initially, a reduction of approximately 5% is observed, corresponding to the dehydration process. Subsequently, a significant decrease in the mass of the sample is observed around 221°C, indicating the beginning of the decomposition of the inulin chains. Examination of the derivative of mass as a function of temperature highlights that the maximum degradation temperature is approximately 232°C, with a second peak of lesser magnitude at 268°C. This behavior suggests that there is variability in the chain size of the carbohydrates that make up inulin. Finally, at the end of the temperature increase to 600°C, a total mass loss of 77% is reached. These results are in agreement with those found by [15].

For the cookie samples in Figure 2b, it is observed that the curves have a great similarity between them, due to the similarity presented in the formulations. Three peaks are visualized, corresponding to the degradation of the different components of the formulations. According to comparisons with literature, the observed behavior was associated as follows: The first peak is mainly due to the degradation of sucrose and inulin, with the maximum peak recorded at 225°C [15, 22], the second peak is mainly due to the degradation of gluten proteins and wheat flour at 293°C [23, 24], the last peak was recorded at 385°C and is related to the degradation of butter fats. For this last peak, it could not be corroborated exactly that the degradation of butter fats occurs at this temperature, however, it was compared with the degradation temperature of other fats, which are in the same temperature range. For example, the maximum peak of degradation of fat extracted from goat milk and goat milk chocolate is 388°C and 410°C respectively [25], as well as Sacha inchi seed oil with temperature ranges between 380°C and 440°C [26], or the degradation of shea butter observed in the range of 360°C to 400°C [27].

It is important to note that, when considering the beginning of the range of thermal degradation of the components of the formulations, it is suggested that for baking processes or other thermal treatments, temperatures of 210°C should not be exceeded, so that the properties and nutritional functions of the inulin are not affected. Inulin would maintain its nature and chemical structure intact at temperatures below this limit.

3.3 Moisture content

The results for moisture content are presented in Table 2. It can be seen that the formulations presented a low moisture content, in a range between 3.61% and 2.13%, which is within the normal range for baked cookies [28]. At the same time, it complies with the standard established in Colombia for moisture in this type of product (less than 14%), regulated in the NTC 1241 standard [29].

The analysis of variance showed that the means of the sample groups were not significantly equal to each other, due to a p value equal to 0.000, with a significance level of 0.05. In addition, Fisher's 95% confidence interval test showed that the control and RG formulas were equal to each other, and there were significant differences for both RA and RGA. The control and RG group obtained the highest values for water content, with 3.50% and 3.61%, respectively, followed in descending order by RA with 2.72% and finally RGA with 2.13%.

These results suggest that the type and amount of ingredient replacement (fat and sugar by inulin) have a significant impact on the moisture content of the cookies. Comparing the observed results with the literature, certain correlations are observed. First, for cookies with 25% to 50% replacement of sugar content by inulin, it is observed that there is no effect on the moisture content of the product [11, 30]. On the other hand, for those cookies where the fat content is replaced by inulin, it is observed that there is a direct decrease in the amount replaced [12, 31].

3.4 Water Activity (A_w)

The results for the water activity of the cookies are specified in Table 2.

Table 2. Physicochemical test results: Moisture content, water activity, hardness, and fracturability.

Group	Humidity (%)	A_w	Hardness (N)	Fracturability (mm)
Control	3.50 ^a (0.41)	0.359 ^a (0.016)	29.26 ^a (2.07)	0.440 ^a (0.094)
RG	3.61 ^a (0.25)	0.324 ^b (0.005)	63.70 ^c (4.23)	0.459 ^a (0.171)
RA	2.72 ^b (0.25)	0.245 ^c (0.016)	26.12 ^a (4.03)	0.436 ^a (0.097)
RGA	2.13 ^c (0.10)	0.359 ^a (0.016)	37.02 ^a (2.29)	0.343 ^a (0.090)

Values in parentheses are the standard deviation. For the same column, different letters represent statistically significant differences according to Fisher's test ($p < 0.05$).

It is observed that all the means of the formulations presented a low value for the water activity index, related to their low moisture content, therefore, it is positive that there are not sufficient conditions for the rapid proliferation of microorganisms in the feed [18]. The analysis of variance indicated that the group means for the water activity results were different from each other, obtaining a p-value equal to 0.000.

In addition, Fisher's interval test indicated that all groups were different from each other when compared individually. This effect of the replacement in the formulations on the water activity factor was evidenced by a decrease in the same. Likewise, it was observed that the lowest water activity value was obtained by the RGA group, which was the same group that obtained the lowest moisture content value.

However, a comparison with the literature shows certain variations to the results obtained by other authors for formulations with inulin replacements. On the one hand, for those cookies with sugar replacement, a slight decrease in the water activity of the cookie was observed for replacements of 50% of the sugar content [30], but for replacements of 25% and 30%, no effect was observed [11]. On the other hand, an effect on water activity proportional to the fat content of the cookie substituted by inulin was observed [12, 31]. In general, the water activity of the cookie and any product will be related to the moisture content present, as observed in the results obtained, where the lowest activity results are consistent with the lowest moisture values [32].

In this case, the results were favorable and it is concluded that the cookies present optimal values to ensure their preservation for long periods, under storage conditions at room temperature and low humidity [33]. However, further studies are suggested to determine the shelf life of the product.

3.5 Texture

Texture is a group of properties that depend on the structure and chemical composition. In this case, the measurement of hardness and practicability was chosen to represent the texture of the product. The hardness of the cookie is understood as the maximum stress that the sample can withstand before reaching mechanical failure, i.e., when it fractures. On the other hand, tractability is the distance at which that maximum force is received, which occurs at the fracture of the material. For this case, the three-point test simulates the stress at the commensal bite [34].

Table 2 shows the means of the results obtained in the texture test, which correspond to the value of the peaks in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Representative stress vs. displacement behavior for the hardness of the sample groups.

According to the ANOVA results, the means of the sample groups for the hardness factor were statistically different from each other. Fisher's test showed that only the control group and the RA group were statistically equal, while RG and RGA each formed a statistically isolated group. On the other hand, the results of the practicability test establish that there were no statistical differences between the four groups, according to the analysis of variance. It can be seen that the means for the control group and RA are the lowest, being 29.26 N and 26.12 N respectively. In ascending order, RGA is followed by RGA with 37.02 N and RG with 63.70 N.

In the first observation, an increase in the hardness of the cookies is highlighted as the replacement of butter by inulin increases. This finding is in agreement with previous research, where the replacement of fats with inulin is associated with a significant increase in the firmness of the product [12][13]. According to several authors, this phenomenon is attributed to the fact that fats incorporate and retain tiny air bubbles during the dough mixing process, which expand during baking, generating pores in the structure and resulting in a fine and soft texture in the cookie [35]. Therefore, as the butter content decreases, its effect on texture is reduced. This effect is not observed in the cookie that undergoes exclusively a replacement in sugar content, since it shows a hardness statistically equivalent to the control cookie. Other studies have reported that there are no changes in hardness due to the modification of sugar content by inulin [11, 30].

Figure 3 shows a representative behavior of each sample group, taking into account the average hardness and tractability of each group. The aforementioned hypothesis is more clearly visualized, where the cookies that had their fat content replaced by inulin present higher peaks in the graph, showing the effect of the increase in hardness. On the other hand, the shape presented for the curves shows that the cookies behave as a brittle material. This is because after reaching the maximum stress point, there is no deformation of the material, producing the breakage of the material, represented in the abrupt decrease of the curve [11].

3.6 Colorimetry

The results of the colorimetry test are presented in Table 3. Using an analysis of variance, it was determined that there were no significant differences in the L^* and b^* parameters concerning the control group. On the

other hand, for the parameter a^* , which corresponds to the green-red coordinates in the CIELab system, significant differences were found. According to Fisher's intervals, it is observed that, statistically, parameter a^* was equal in the control and RA formulation.

On the other hand, RG and RGA cookies showed variations: RG presented a decrease in the value of the parameter, indicating a less red color; while in RGA the opposite behavior was observed, an increase in the direction of the red color.

The results obtained in this study corroborate the conclusions drawn from previous investigations, where independent replacements of inulin instead of sugar content or fat content were carried out. Regarding the substitution of sugar content, no significant alterations in brightness, changes in the red-green color scale, or the yellow-blue color range were evident [11]. In contrast, several authors have documented decreases in the a^* parameter as a consequence of the use of inulin, maltodextrin, and polydextrose as fat substitutes in baked products, with a more pronounced effect as the substituted content increases [36].

However, other sources suggest that no significant variations in L^* , a^* , or b^* parameters should be seen when using inulin as a partial substitute for fat content [13]. Inulin, being a fructan and thus a chain of fructose units, does not participate in the Maillard reaction or other reactions that affect color during processing, since it is not considered a reducing sugar. In this sense, it is postulated that possible effects could be related to disparities in baking conditions. It should be noted that no associated effects have been previously documented for the simultaneous replacement of sugar and fat content, as occurs in the RGA formulation.

An overall color evaluation was performed by comparing ΔE , obtained by formula (1), which compares the means of the parameters of each cookie formulation with that of the control group. As shown in Table 3, the ΔE values were greater than 1 but less than 3, which means that some color differences are perceptible to the human eye. However, they cannot be classified as obvious differences.

These results suggest that there are appreciable color differences that may or may not affect the public's perception of certain formulations. It should be taken into account that the color of the food is the first information that the consumer receives about the product, which can generate the rejection or acceptance of the product [13].

Table 3. Results of colorimetry tests and calculation of ΔE .

Group	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE
Control	29.5 ^{ab} (2.9)	8.6 ^b (0.8)	17.9 ^a (1.4)	-- --
RG	31.2 ^a (2.7)	7.4 ^a (0.7)	17.9 ^a (1.0)	2,10
RA	30.2 ^{ab} (2.9)	8.6 ^b (0.8)	17.6 ^a (1.7)	0,75
RGA	29.0 ^c (2.4)	10.1 ^c (0.6)	17.4 ^a (1.8)	1,68

Values in parentheses are the standard deviation. For the same column, different letters represent statistically significant differences according to Fisher's test ($p < 0.05$).

3.7 Sensory analysis

The sensory analysis was carried out through a survey involving 50 people, 40% men, and 60% women, with no previous experience in sensory evaluation. Within this population, the distribution of participants was divided into age groups as follows: 16% were between 18 and 25 years old, 30% were between 26 and 35 years old, 34% ranged between 36 and 45 years old, and 20% were over 45 years old, with the oldest person being 60 years old. Regarding the consumption habits of cookies, 38% of the respondents consumed them sporadically, followed by 36% who consumed them weekly, 14% with monthly consumption, and 12% who consumed them daily.

Table 4 shows the results of the hedonic scales used in the surveys, where the maximum response for each attribute is 9. First, for the attribute of the overall taste of the cookies, the analysis of variance concluded that there are no significant differences in the overall acceptance of the new formulations.

Table 4. Means obtained by surveys for Overall Taste, Appearance, Texture, Color and Flavor.

Group	Global Taste	Appearance	Texture	Color	Taste
Control	7.1 ^a (2.0)	7.5 ^a (1.8)	7.3 ^a (1.9)	7.7 ^a (1.6)	7.4 ^a (1.9)
RG	6.8 ^a (1.9)	7.5 ^a (1.5)	6.6 ^{bc} (2.2)	7.8 ^a (1.1)	7.1 ^a (1.7)
RA	7.2 ^a (1.7)	7.5 ^a (1.6)	7.4 ^{ab} (1.7)	7.5 ^a (1.7)	7.3 ^a (1.7)
RGA	7.0 ^a (2.0)	6.8 ^a (1.9)	6.4 ^c (1.9)	6.6 ^b (1.9)	7.0 ^b (1.9)

Values in parentheses are the standard deviation. For the same column, different letters represent statistically significant differences according to Fisher's test ($p < 0.05$).

In relation to Appearance and Flavor attributes, no significant differences were found according to the analysis of variance. On the other hand, Texture and Color scores were affected by the modifications made to the formulations. With respect to texture, it was observed that both the control and RA formulations obtained the highest scores according to the perception of the respondents. The RG and RGA cookies, on the other hand, obtained a decrease in the acceptance of their texture, since they were perceived as more solid and consistent when chewed. These results are congruent with previous findings in the texturometer tests, where these same formulations showed higher values for hardness.

On the other hand, the color differences quantified above seem to have affected only the RGA cookie, which obtained a significant decrease in this section concerning the rest of the formulations. Analyzing in detail the averages of the parameters L^* , a^* , and b^* in Table 3, this cookie obtained the lowest value of luminosity and at the same time obtained the most reddish coloration (a^*), so this combination results in a cookie with an opaque brown color. This is consistent with subsequent comments received from some respondents, where they stated that this cookie was characterized by its brown color, and gave the impression that it had been overcooked, this being an undesirable characteristic.

In general, the results for the attributes obtained using the hedonic scale were satisfactory. A high acceptance is demonstrated for all formulations, obtaining means higher than 7 for almost all attributes of each cookie, which exceeds the value of *I am indifferent* (5), approaching the *I like it*. On the other hand, it is worth noting the performance of the RA cookie, which for all attributes was statistically equal to the Control sample. On the other hand, the RG and RGA formulations obtained appreciable decreases in the attributes of texture and color, which, although they do not seem to affect the overall taste of the public, could be reviewed. These results position RA as the best prototype to consider for the production of a functional food.

Other authors obtained similar results in sensory analyses. Laguna et al [30] report that no differences were obtained concerning the control in the attributes scored for a formulation that replaces 25% of the sugar content with inulin. At the same time, they point out that higher contents (50%) have negative effects on all the attributes evaluated. On the other hand, in [13] they documented that for replacements of 30% and higher for fat content, decreases in general acceptance were obtained, mainly due to changes in texture and flavor.

In relation to the evaluations made using the JAR scale, responses revealed that a segment of respondents perceived the crunchiness levels of the four formulations to be high, with at least 20% of participants reporting this indicator for each formulation, as seen in Figure 4. Specifically, the RG and RGA cookies were considered by most respondents to be very crunchy with 62% and 74%, respectively, about this attribute.

Figure 4. JAR results for the four formulations

In addition, for both RG and RGA, no overall acceptance was observed for sweetness, again recording values above 20% for the *Very sweet* attribute. Despite these negative perceptions concerning the RG and RGA formulations, these deviations did not translate into a decrease in overall acceptance, as evidenced in the penalty analysis carried out, which is recorded in Table 4.

Percentage of judges in each group and penalties for each attribute.

Sample	Attribute	Group	% Judges	Penalty
Control	<i>Sweetness</i>	- Sweet	14	1.56
		+ Sweet	18	1.56
	<i>Crocancia</i>	- Crunchy	18	1.23
		+ Crocante	34	1.15
RG	<i>Sweetness</i>	- Sweet	14	0.14
		+ Sweet	30	0.19
	<i>Crocancia</i>	- Crunchy	16	1.23
		+ Crunchy	62	-0.14
RA	<i>Sweetness</i>	- Sweet	6	1.78
		+ Sweet	18	0.78
	<i>Crocancia</i>	- Crunchy	10	0.85
		+ Crocante	38	0.29
RGA	<i>Sweetness</i>	- Sweet	12	-0.20
		+ Sweet	34	0.02
	<i>Crocancia</i>	- Crunchy	6	0.96
		+ Crocante	74	-0.15

The penalty attribute helps to distinguish whether there is an effect of the attributes on the overall acceptance of the product, being considered an unimportant effect if the penalty is less than 1 or if the percentage of judges with values different from JAR is less than 20% [27]. In contrast, the control and RA formulations exhibited superior performance in the sweetness aspect, with RA standing out with 76% in the JAR attribute. However, it should be noted that the Control cookie experienced a significant penalty in overall acceptance due to the *Very crispy* attribute, with a penalty value of 1.15 for 34% of the evaluators.

In terms of final opinions, respondents expressed that 52% would be willing to purchase the control cookie, 44% would opt for the RA cookie, while only 14% and 12% would be inclined to purchase the RG and RGA cookies, respectively. In addition, 50% indicated their willingness to purchase a 30 g presentation within a price range between \$1000 and COP 2000, 34% in the range of \$2000 to COP 3000, and only 16% would be willing to pay more than COP 3000.

In the Colombian market, no cookies containing inulin in their formulation were found, so the values were compared with cookies with fiber, whose cost ranges between \$1701 and COP 3360 for 30 g of product. Consequently, considering the prices of similar products in the market, it can be concluded that the price range suggested by the respondents is within an average and acceptable range for commercialization.

In light of the results of the sensory analysis, the positive responses to the control and RA formulations, which achieved the best acceptance among the participants, stand out. Therefore, it is concluded that, among the new formulations designed, RA is presented as optimal for use as a new functional food. A cost analysis of the raw materials for the production of RA determined that the cost of the materials alone for the 30 g presentation is approximately COP 832, a value that could be reduced through a study that optimizes the choice of brands and suppliers. To set a selling price for the product, it would be necessary to conduct a more detailed market study, considering the profit margin and costs inherent to the value chain, such as energy consumption, investment in equipment, packaging process, advertising, logistics, etc.

3.8 Nutritional content

A theoretical analysis of the nutritional content of the RA formulation, identified as the best among the new formulations, as detailed in the previous analysis, was carried out. The most relevant data are presented in Table 6, both for 100 g of cookie and for the 30 g standard portion. The structure of the table follows the guidelines established in Resolution 810 of 2021, which regulates food labeling in Colombia [38].

Table 6. Theoretical nutritional information type labeled RA formulation.

Serving Size: 2 cookies (30 g)		
Servings per container: 1		
	Per 100 g	Per serving
Calories (kcal)	414	124
Total fat	20.3 g	6.1 g
Saturated fat	9.5 g	2.8 g
Trans Fat	0 g	0 g
Carbohydrates	51 g	15 g
Dietary fiber	6.4 g	1.9 g
Total sugars	14 g	4.1 g
Added sugars	13 g	4 g
Protein	6 g	1.9 g
Sodium	117 mg	35 mg
Iron	0.8 mg	0.2 mg

The information gathered is crucial to obtain an overview of the nutritional contribution of the product. The substantial fiber contribution stands out, which is at least 6.4 g per 100 g of food. This would indicate that the product can be considered an excellent source of fiber, according to resolution 810 of 2021 [38].

However, according to the above results, this contribution could be further improved by increasing the inulin content in the formulation. In addition, other positive aspects are observed, such as the absence of trans fats and the low sodium content. The substitution of 30% of the sugar content led to a caloric reduction of 4.6% and a five-fold increase in the amount of fiber compared to the control formulation.

However, according to the same resolution previously mentioned, the new product will require mandatory warning stamps for its commercialization [38], indicating a high content of added sugars and saturated fats that exceed the established limits. The suggested warning stamps on the packaging are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Required front warning seal

Although these aspects are not directly related to the central objective of the research, they are crucial considerations for the future development of the product. The presence of these labels may affect product acceptance and purchase, as they could result in additional taxes and an increase in price for the consumer. In addition, these warnings are designed to discourage the consumption of products considered harmful or not nutritious. Therefore, it is suggested to initially explore alternatives to reduce or replace the sugar content in the product. Likewise, it is recommended to investigate the use of other fats and adjust the percentages in the formulation, both suggestions aimed at ensuring that sugar and fat levels do not exceed the limits established in Resolution 810 of 2021 [38].

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the analysis of cookie properties, similar behavior was found in the TGA curves for all samples, with three peaks identified in the degradation of cookie components. Those with replacement had lower moisture content and water activity due to the low water retention capacity of inulin. Texture varied, with the RA cookie maintaining the original texture, while the variants with fat replacement showed significant increases in intractability.

In the color measurements, the cookies with fat replacement presented a reddish tone, unlike the RA cookie, which retained the original color. In the sensory analysis, all formulations were generally accepted, but the

control and RA cookies obtained higher scores, showing higher purchase intention. It is suggested that the development of the RA cookie is feasible due to its optimal properties and high public acceptance. In addition, in a theoretical nutritional analysis, it was found that the cookie can be considered an excellent source of fiber, which was the initially proposed target for the functional food.

Considering the positive results obtained with the RA cookie, it is suggested to explore formulations with sugar substitutions higher than 30% to determine optimal replacement ranges. This approach will expand the understanding of formulation possibilities and provide valuable information for future research and development in the field of improved food products.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bradford B. (1970). Overview of what functional foods are. *Drug Discovery and Evaluation: Pharmacological Assays*. Omega.
- [2] Cortés R. et al. (2005). Alimentos Funcionales: Una historia con mucho presente y futuro. *Revista de la Facultad de Química Farmacéutica* 12(1).
- [3] Illippangama A. et al. (2022). Inulin as a functional ingredient and their applications in meat products. *Carbohydrate Polymers*.
- [4] Franck A. (2002). Technological functionality of inulin and oligofructose. *The British Journal of Nutrition*.
- [5] Roberfroid M. (2007). Inulin-type fructans: Functional Food Ingredients. *The Journal of Nutrition*.
- [6] Roberfroid M. (2002). Functional Food concept and its application to prebiotics. *Digestive and Liver Disease*.
- [7] Roberfroid M. (1999). Concepts in functional foods: The case of inulin and oligofructose. *The Journal of Nutrition*.
- [8] Lingyun W. et al. (2006). Studies on the extracting technical conditions of inulin from Jerusalem artichoke tubers. *Journal of Food Engineering*.
- [9] Instituto de la Galleta. (2018). Galletas y Nutrición. Recuperado: <http://institutodelagalleta.com/galletas/Nutricion.php?cl=2>
- [10] Mieszkowska A. y Marzec A. (2016). Effect of polydextrose and inulin on texture and consumer preference of short-dough biscuits with chickpea flour.
- [11] Rodriguez J. et al. (2022). Soluble fibres as sucrose replacers: Effects on physical and sensory properties of sugar-reduced short-dough biscuits. *LWT*, 167.
- [12] Laguna L. et al. (2014). HPMC and inulin as fat replacers in biscuits: Sensory and instrumental evaluation. *LWT*.
- [13] Krystyan M. et al. (2015). The effect of inulin as a fat replacement on dough and biscuit properties. *Journal of Food Quality*.
- [14] Blecker C. et al. (2003). Characterisation of different inulin samples by DSC: Influence of polymerisation degree on melting temperature. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*.
- [15] Wahbi W. et al. (2020). Novel inulin electrospun composite nanofibers: Prebiotic and antibacterial activities. *ACS Omega*.
- [16] López Y. et al. (2022). Valorization strategies for a by-product of organic tomato processing as potential ingredient in functional food formulations. *Frontiers*.
- [17] Carranza C. (2020). Manejo de las fórmulas de diferencias de color vs límites de aceptabilidad. Centro Nacional de Metrología México. Recuperado: <https://www.cenam.mx/memorias/descarga/simposio%202002/doctos/te017.pdf>
- [18] Ahn J. et al. (2014). Comparison of oven-drying methods for determination of moisture content in feed ingredients. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences*.
- [19] Cardona F. (2019). Actividad del agua en alimentos: concepto, medida y aplicaciones. *RiuNet Repositorio UPV*.
- [20] Zimeri J. y Kokini J. (2002). The effect of moisture content on the crystallinity and glass transition temperature of inulin. *Carbohydrate Polymers*.
- [21] Leyva C. et al. (2015). Chemical, thermal and physical characterization of inulin for its technological application based on the degree of polymerization. *Journal of Food Process Engineering*.
- [22] Chen H. et al. (2012). Pyrolysis characteristics of sucrose biomass in a tubular reactor and a thermogravimetric analysis. *Fuel*.
- [23] Nawrocka A. et al. (2017). Effect of dietary fibre polysaccharides on structure and thermal properties of gluten proteins e A study on gluten dough with application of FT-Raman spectroscopy, TGA and DSC. *Food Hydrocolloids*. Rama.
- [24] Mengelöglu F. y Karakus K. (2008). Thermal degradation, mechanical properties and morphology of wheat straw flour filled recycled thermoplastic composites. *MDPI*.
- [25] Dolatowska K. et al. (2019). Characterization of thermal properties of goat milk fat and goat milk chocolate by using DSC, PDSC and TGA methods. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*.
- [26] Mendoza D. y Meneses J. (2022). Desarrollo de encapsulados de Aceite de Semilla de Sacha Inchi para la formulación de Alimentos Funcionales. *Repositorio Institucional Séneca*.
- [27] Darmawan M. et al. (2021). Preparation and characterisation of indigenous Tengkwang (*Shorea Stenoptera*) Butter for food and cosmetics material. *Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences*.
- [28] Mamat H. et al. (2010). Physicochemical properties of commercial semi-sweet biscuit. *Food Chemistry*.
- [29] ICONTEC. (2007). NTC 1241: Productos de Molinería. Galletas. Recuperado: <https://tienda.icontec.org/gp-productos-de-molineria-galletas-ntc1241-2007.html>
- [30] Laguna L. et al. (2013). Inulin and erythritol as sucrose replacers in short-dough cookies: Sensory, fracture, and acoustic properties. *Journal of Food Science*.
- [31] Sayed H. y Khalil S. (2017). Effect of chicory inulin extract as a fat replacer on texture and sensory properties of cookies. *Middle East Journal of Applied Sciences*.
- [32] Hough G. et al. (2007). Sensory texture of commercial biscuits as a function of water activity. *Journal of Texture*.

- [33] Bertagnolli S. et al. (2014). Bioactive compounds and acceptance of cookies made with guava peel flour. *Ciência e Tecnologia de Alimentos*.
- [34] Woody A. (2003). Probing and three-point bend methods compared to sensory scales as measurements for cookie texture. Tennessee Research and Creative Exchange.
- [35] Akoh C. y Lee K. (2007). Physical properties of trans-free bakery shortening produced by lipase-catalyzed Interesterification. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society*.
- [36] Serin S. y Sayar S. (2016). The effect of the replacement of fat with carbohydrate-based fat replacers on the dough properties and quality of the baked pogaca: A traditional high-fat bakery product. *Food Science and Technology*.
- [37] Fernandez I. et al. (2018). Aplicación de las Escalas de Punto ideal O just-about-right (JAR) en análisis sensorial de Alimentos. *Omega*.
- [38] MEN. (2021). Resolución número 810 de 2021. Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social. Recuperado: https://www.minsalud.gov.co/Normatividad_Nuevo/Resoluci%C3%B3n%20No.%20810de%202021.pdf